

SPIRITUALITY, ACCOUNTING AND TRANSPARENT FINANCIAL REPORTING IN DELTA AND EDO STATES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Based on a survey research approach, this study examines the relationship between spirituality accounting and transparent financial reporting in Delta and Edo States, Nigeria, in light of the collapse of numerous multinational giants as a result of audit problems. Honesty and conscience were used to represent spirituality accounting, while transparency was adopted as a proxy for transparent financial reporting. A questionnaire with a 96% response rate was used to gather primary data from a sample of 78 professional accountants who are members of ICAN or ANAN and who work in the finance and accounts departments of their respective state ministries, departments, and agencies. The sample of 78 accountants was determined from a population of 166 professional accountants using the Taro Yamane formula. Descriptive statistics and Pearson rank correlation were used to analyze the data. The results demonstrated a strong correlation between honesty, conscience, and transparency. The study concluded that spirituality accounting has a significant relationship with transparent financial reporting. To ensure a well-rounded understanding among employees, it was recommended that accountants disclose all pertinent information that could impact the intended audience's comprehension of financial reports. Furthermore, it was recommended that spirituality accounting principles be clearly communicated during employee orientation.

KEYWORDS: Accounting, Conscience, Ethics, Honesty, Transparency

INTRODUCTION

Several authors have examined the concept of spirituality in relation to accounting practices (Bryer, 2000; Chiapello, 2007; Derks, 2008). All of them, in one way or another, support the view that accounting embodies the values of capitalism, which emphasize profit maximization. However, since greed destroys lives—as demonstrated by the Enron, WorldCom, and Tyco scandals of 2002—and because profit maximization is not the ultimate goal of life, the concept of spirituality accounting was introduced to address these issues and reduce the dominance of capitalistic, individualistic, materialistic, and secular (CIMS) values in accounting.

After considering the foregoing explanation, one may question whether accounting represents only the values of capitalism, materialism, individualism, and secularism. Does accounting not also embody other values, such as spiritual values, that can influence transparency in financial reporting?

Spirituality accounting is not a new concept in accounting terminology. It is a non-denominational concept that deals with the innate abilities of human beings. Many individuals may react with skepticism when spirituality is mentioned as a research topic in accounting, particularly when it is linked to transparency in accounting practice and financial reporting.

In the wake of high-profile corporate failures involving companies such as Enron, WorldCom, Arthur Andersen, Tyco International, Adelphia, Cadbury PLC, and Lever Brothers PLC, the issue of business ethics has received renewed global attention (Okaro et al., 2013). As a result of these failures, transparency in financial reporting has come under serious scrutiny.

Several scholars—Berger and Hefner (2003), Finke (2003), Iannaccone and Klick (2003), Malloch (2008), Urban (2003), Verter (2003), and Woodberry (2003)—have investigated spirituality in relation to accounting practices, producing varying and sometimes conflicting results due to the different dimensions used as proxies for spirituality. Their findings reveal a lack of consensus, thereby creating a gap in the literature and providing room for further investigation.

This study investigates the relationship between spirituality accounting and transparent financial reporting in Delta and Edo States, Nigeria, in the context of high-profile business scandals caused by audit compromise. Spirituality accounting, as the independent variable, was represented by honesty and conscience, while transparency served as the dependent variable and a proxy for transparent financial reporting. The remainder of the paper covers the review of related literature, methodology, results and discussion, and summary, conclusion, and recommendations.

Spirituality Accounting

According to Kluger (2004), spirituality is something that every person experiences, regardless of whether they identify as religious, humanist, hedonist, or atheist. A person's lack of religious affiliation is often cited as the reason they claim to be spiritually uninterested. The significance of these claims lies in their ability to disprove the assumption that any one religion or faith has a monopoly on spirituality. Instead, spirituality is shown to be a universal trait shared by all people.

The term *sacred* is often used interchangeably with spirituality. To be spiritual, one must accept that each individual life serves a greater purpose and possesses inherent importance (Sheep, 2003; Pandey & Gupta, 2008). Individuals who identify as spiritual often experience a sense of connectedness to something higher than themselves. Such individuals tend to be more concerned with changing and improving the world rather than focusing solely on self-improvement. Spiritual practices are typically personal and intimate in nature (McClung et al., 2006).

According to Sarah and Hershey (2015), performing good deeds and living a purposeful life are central to spirituality. If life extends beyond what is immediately visible, businesses should strive to improve society for their employees and the consumers of their products and services. Although firms have a duty to maximize profits, this does not preclude them from considering the interests of stakeholders such as society, investors, and users of financial reports. Consequently, it is important to integrate spirituality into accounting reports so that financial statements are prepared with a clear conscience, truthfulness, honesty, and sincerity.

Collins and Kakabadse (2006) define spirituality as having a sense of community with others. It is environmentally friendly because it emphasizes achieving more with less harm to the planet, while also uniting one's spirituality, vocation, and family toward positive social change. In Western Europe, the public-private divide is often emphasized to distinguish between religious belief and religious practice.

In *The Spiritual Life*, Lozano and Raimon (2004) argue that spirituality is central to personal fulfillment and social well-being. Spiritual growth involves refining one's sensibilities in order to perceive the deeper nuances of the world. Spirituality is not a rigid set of rules or a prescribed lifestyle, but rather a fundamental mindset. Consequently, spirituality and religion are distinct yet overlapping concepts in both formal education and everyday discourse (Bouckaert, 2004).

Fogel (2000), in *Is Spirituality Significant in the American Economy?*, extensively discusses the relevance of spirituality to modern business. He identifies fifteen essential spiritual resources, including belonging to a group, awareness of opportunities, strong family ethics, a clear sense of purpose, a strong work ethic, and healthy self-worth. He argues that for capitalism to thrive in the modern economy, spiritual principles must be incorporated.

Rhodes (2006) similarly acknowledges that employees are better able to explore their creative potential when supported by a spiritual workplace. Spiritually inclined employees seek to integrate their faith into their work and daily lives. As a result, individuals benefit from working in organizations that do not exploit employees merely to increase profits or reward executives excessively. Such employees desire to contribute positively to society and make a meaningful difference.

Karakas (2010) analyzed approximately 140 studies related to spirituality and concluded that spirituality improves employees' health and happiness, provides meaning and direction in work, and fosters a sense of community. He argues that organizations should treat employees with dignity and trust rather than exploiting them for financial gain. Spirituality is fundamentally incompatible with viewing workers as disposable components of a production process. Instead, it requires providing meaningful employment that respects workers' skills and creativity (Byrne, 2005).

Honesty

Ray (2019) asserts that investors must be able to trust the information presented in financial reports; therefore, honesty, integrity, and transparency are essential. Managers rely on accurate accounting information to operate businesses without concern for bias or misrepresentation. The critical element in financial decision-making lies in maintaining honesty within accounting practices.

Ray further explains that Generally Accepted Accounting Principles (GAAP) were developed to ensure consistency, honesty, and transparency in financial reporting. Similarly, International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) promote uniformity and comparability, thereby reducing the likelihood of fraud and errors. When questions arise regarding any aspect of a financial report, accountants can consult GAAP to determine appropriate procedures.

Conscience

Jeffrey (2006) notes that although consciousness is frequently discussed, its functioning remains poorly understood. Conscience is often perceived as an internal voice that condemns actions violating personal moral values. Individuals frequently cite conscience as motivation for actions such as pursuing public office or engaging in warfare. Jeffrey builds a theory of mind centered on conscience to explain its broad influence, combining insights from neuroscience and long-standing philosophical traditions.

His work focuses on revisiting fundamental philosophical questions such as “What does it all mean?” and led to the development of an Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) framework informed by neuroscience. This framework provides a basis for analyzing ethical dilemmas without reducing morality to a secondary concern.

Jeffrey further explores conscience as humanity’s most pressing moral force, exemplified by ethical challenges such as global warming. He argues that conscience is a mental process that generates emotional and logical responses aligned with an individual’s moral compass. Unlike reactions driven by external stimuli, conscience operates internally and often manifests as guilt when moral principles are violated. Religious traditions often view conscience as innate morality, divine guidance, or an inner voice—frequently described as the “voice within” or “inner light.”

Financial Reporting Quality

Siriyama and Norah (2017) conducted a literature review examining recent studies on the measurement and determinants of financial reporting quality. Focusing on publications between 2009 and 2015, the study identified gaps in the literature, including incomplete data and insufficient sample sizes. The findings highlighted the need for more comprehensive research and offered valuable insights into the dimensions of high-quality financial reporting.

Loveday (2017) examined audit quality practices and financial reporting in Nigeria using data from auditing firms. Employing descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and stepwise multiple regression, the study found a positive relationship between financial reporting quality and audit indicators such as auditor independence, technical training, and engagement performance. Auditor independence accounted for 47.9% of the variance in financial report reliability, underscoring its importance in credible financial reporting.

Theoretical Framework

Derrida’s Deconstruction Theory

This study is grounded in Jacques Derrida’s deconstruction theory, proposed in the late 1960s. The theory emphasizes values beyond relevance and reliability, highlighting deeper

qualitative aspects of financial reporting. According to Al-Fayyadl (2005), Derrida's concept of "otherness" supports transparency, truth-telling, and faithful documentation of transactions. Deconstruction encourages the revelation of truth through observation and critical reflection, ensuring that financial transactions are factual, objective, and open to independent verification.

Empirical Review

Bushi (2019) examined accounting ethics and professionalism in Nigeria, using competence and independence as indicators of ethics and reliability and understandability as measures of reporting quality. Using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), the study found significant relationships between ethical standards and financial reporting quality, leading to recommendations for ethics compliance departments in organizations.

Adesanya et al. (2019) investigated ethical principles and the relevance of financial reporting among listed Nigerian companies. Their findings revealed a strong relationship between ethical standards and report relevance, emphasizing the need for continuous ethical focus among accountants and auditors.

Michael et al. (2019) assessed the prospects and challenges of IFRS implementation in Nigeria, concluding that while global standards are applied, weak corporate governance remains a major obstacle. The study recommended updating accounting reports to include indigenous languages.

Mehta and Moonat (2017) found that spiritually oriented accountants are better prepared to handle ethical challenges. They advocated for integrating moral and spiritual development into accounting education.

Claudia and Lucia (2016) explored qualitative aspects of accounting information, highlighting the challenges accountants face when exercising professional judgment.

Iwan (2015) examined how spirituality within the accounting profession's code of ethics can awaken conscience and moral responsibility, advocating for holistic ethical certification standards. Seyedhossein (2014) analyzed the impact of auditors' spiritual and human capital on independent audit opinions in Iran, concluding that both significantly influence audit quality and investor trust.

Methodology

This study adopted a survey research design based on primary data collected from professional accountants who are members of the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN) or the Association of National Accountants of Nigeria (ANAN). The respondents work in the finance and accounts departments of various ministries, departments, and agencies in Delta and Edo States, Nigeria.

The research instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire, which was administered systematically to the selected respondents.

Study Population and Sample

The study population comprised 166 professional accountants drawn from the records of state districts or branches of the respective professional institutes as of January 31, 2020. The study sample was determined using the Taro Yamane formula, resulting in a sample size of 78 professional accountants, as presented in Table 1.

According to Baridom (2001), the Taro Yamane formula is expressed as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n is the desired sample size, N is the population size and e is the significance level.

Table 1; Sample Size

S/No	States	Population	Sample size
1	Delta	76	36
2	Edo	90	42
	Total	166	78

Source: Survey Data, 2022

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{166}{1 + 166(0.05)^2} \\ &= \frac{166}{1 + 166(0.0025)} \\ &= \frac{166}{1 + 1.125} \\ &= \frac{166}{2.125} \\ &= 78.12 = 78 \text{ approximately} \end{aligned}$$

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed on a five-point Likert scale measured on an interval basis to elicit information on the relationship between spirituality accounting and transparent financial reporting in Delta and Edo States, Nigeria. The response options were structured as follows: **Strongly Agree (5), Agree (4), Undecided (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1).**

The questionnaire comprised two sections. **Section One** contained the respondents' bio-data, including name, age, sex, level of education, and marital status. **Section Two** consisted of questions measuring the study variables, namely the independent variables (spirituality accounting dimensions) and the dependent variable (transparent financial reporting).

Validity and Reliability

The questionnaire was developed based on content validity to ensure adequate coverage of both the dependent and independent variables of the study. To further enhance validity, the instrument was reviewed and validated by senior academic staff who are also professional accountants.

The test-retest method of reliability was adopted through repeated administration of the questionnaire during a pilot study. The instrument was first administered to 20 respondents drawn from the two states, with 10 respondents selected from each state.

The reliability of the instrument was subsequently established using **Cronbach’s alpha**, which was employed to determine the coefficient of reliability and internal consistency of the instrument. This method measured the degree to which the results of the pilot study corresponded with those of the main field survey. The result of the reliability coefficient is presented in **Table 2**.

Table2:ReliabilityStatistics

CronbachAlpha	NofItems
.825	20

Source:SurveyData,2022

Model Specification

Adapting statistical models previously employed by researchers such as Etale and Yalah (2022) to facilitate the use of Spearman’s rank correlation for data analysis, the model for this study is specified as follows:

$$TPT=f(HON,CON)\text{ }TPT = f(\text{HON}, \text{CON})$$

The functional model is transformed into a linear mathematical equation to ease analysis:

$$TPT=\beta_0+\beta_1HON+\beta_2CON+\mu\text{ }TPT = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{HON} + \beta_2 \text{CON} + \mu$$

Where:

- **TPT** = Transparency
- **HON** = Honesty
- **CON** = Conscience
- **β_0** = Intercept (constant term)
- **β_1, β_2** = Coefficients of the independent variables to be determined
- **μ** = Stochastic error term

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected for this study were analyzed using **Spearman’s rank-order correlation technique**, in line with the model specified above. The analysis was conducted with the aid of the **Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS)** software.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data obtained from the questionnaire-based field survey. The results of the statistical analysis are reported and discussed in relation to the study objectives and hypotheses.

Table3:AdministrationandRetrievalofCopiesofQuestionnaire

NoofQuestionnaireAdministered	NoofQuestionnaireRetrieved	NoofQuestionnaireFounduseful	%ofSuccess
78	75	72	96

Source:SurveyData,2022

Table 3 shows the administration and retrieval of questionnaires. A total of **78 copies** of the questionnaire were administered to the sampled respondents. Out of these, **75 copies** were retrieved after a series of follow-ups, while **72 copies** were found to be properly completed and suitable for analysis. This represents a **96 percent response rate**, which was considered adequate and significant for the study.

Table4:Gender

		Frequency	Percent	ValidPercent	CumulativePercent
Valid	Male	43	60	60	60
	Female	29	40	40	100
	Total	72	100	100	

Source:Surveydata,2022

Table 4 presents the gender distribution of respondents to ensure adequate representation of both males and females in the study. The table indicates that **43 respondents (60 percent)** were male, while **29 respondents (40 percent)** were female.

Table5:HighestEducationlevel

		Frequency	Percent	ValidPercent	CumulativePercent
Valid	NCE	15	20.8	20.8	20.8
	BED	17	23.6	23.6	44.4
	BSC	19	26.4	26.4	70.8
	OTHERS	21	29.2	29.2	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Source:Surveydata,2022

Table 5 presents the educational qualifications of the sampled respondents. The respondents' educational levels range from **NCE** to other higher qualifications. Specifically, **20.8 percent** of the respondents possess an **NCE**, **23.6 percent** hold a **B.Ed**, **26.4 percent** possess a **B.Sc. degree**, while **29.2 percent** have other qualifications not specifically mentioned. From these results, it can be deduced that the sampled respondents are sufficiently knowledgeable and capable of understanding and appropriately interpreting the questionnaire items.

Table6:YearsinAccountingExperience

		Frequency	Percent	ValidPercent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-5Years	18	25.0	25.0	25.0
	6-10Years	25	34.7	34.7	59.7
	11Yearsormore	29	40.3	40.3	100.0
	Total	72	100.0	100.0	

Source: Surveydata, 2022

Table 6 presents the respondents' years of experience in accounting practice. The distribution shows that **25 percent** of respondents have been in the profession for **1–5 years**, **34.7 percent** for **6–10 years**, and **40.3 percent** for **11 years or more**. It can be inferred from these results that the respondents possess adequate knowledge and experience relevant to the study. Therefore, their responses can be considered reliable for the purpose of this research.

Data Analysis Descriptive Statistics

Table7 Descriptive Statistics on Honesty

S/N	Honesty	SA	A	M	D	SD	Agg	\bar{x}
		5	4	3	2	1		
1	I record the exact amount of any financial transaction in the books of account.	93	78	10	8	4	827	4.28
2	I am responsible to my superiors, but my actions are also accountable to God.	101	53	28	6	5	818	4.24
3	I am a sincere and honest person.	55	98	39	0	1	785	4.07
4	I prepare the financial report without any interference or undue influence from management.	38	120	29	3	3	766	3.97
5	1. I am optimistic that the financial report is a true reflection of the	120	60	8	5	0	874	4.53

	organization's financial performance.							
6	I prepare the financial report with sincerity of purpose.	77	109	5	2	0	840	4.35
7	The information I provide in the financial report regarding my assets and liabilities is true and unaltered.	119	46	10	11	7	838	4.34
8	I am very objective and fair in presenting the financial report to management; I do not prioritize anyone's personal interest.	59	123	19	11	0	866	4.49
9	To ensure fairness, I maintain neutrality of interest when preparing the financial report.	136	25	17	9	6	855	4.43
10	I believe in God, which motivates me to be honest and sincere in my professional duties.	98	67	20	4	4	830	4.30

Source: ResearchDesk2022

The analysis of respondents' views on honesty in accounting practice reveals a generally high level of ethical commitment. Respondents strongly agreed that they record the exact amount of any financial transaction in the books of account, with a mean score of 4.28, indicating diligence and accuracy in financial documentation. Similarly, most respondents acknowledged that while they are responsible to their superiors, their actions are also accountable to God (mean score 4.24), reflecting the integration of spirituality into their professional responsibilities. Respondents further indicated that they are sincere and honest individuals (mean score 4.70) and that they prepare financial reports without interference or undue influence from management (mean score 3.97). There was strong agreement (mean score 4.53) that the financial reports they prepare reflect a true and fair view of the organization's financial performance, highlighting their optimism and commitment to transparency. In addition, respondents agreed that they prepare financial reports with sincerity of purpose (mean score 4.35) and that the information presented regarding assets and liabilities is factual and unmanipulated (mean score 4.35). They also reported being objective and fair in presenting financial reports to management (mean score 4.88), as well as maintaining neutrality of interest while preparing such reports (mean score 4.43). Finally, respondents strongly affirmed that their belief in God motivates them to act with honesty and sincerity (mean score 4.30).

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics on Conscience

S/N	Conscience	SA	A	M	D	SD	Agg	\bar{x}
		5	4	3	2	1		
1	I believe that it is wrong to falsify information in a financial report.	147	44	2	0	0	917	4.75
2	My conscience will not allow me to manipulate or cook the figures in a financial report.	108	17	43	25	0	787	4.08
3	My conscience tells me what is right or wrong, so I follow my conscience.	47	56	82	3	5	716	3.71
4	I have conscience.	47	19	117	10	0	682	3.53
5	I feel remorseful when I commit an act that conflicts with my moral values.	125	55	13	0	0	884	4.58
6	I have moral values to protect as an accountant.	150	40	3	0	0	979	5.07
7	I link my moral values to the belief I have in God.	136	47	5	4	1	892	4.62
8	When I am about to make a mistake, I hear my conscience speak to me in a form of “inner voice” or the “voice within” me.	19	57	98	10	9	646	3.35
9	If there is any omission or error in the accounting report I prepared, I do accept such mistakes openly and correct the mistake.	19	59	100	9	6	655	3.39
10	I believe that it is wrong to falsify information in a financial report.	119	55	9	5	5	857	4.44

Source: ResearchDesk2022

The data collected on respondents’ conscience, as shown in Table 8, reveals that the majority of professional accountants strongly adhere to their moral principles in financial reporting. Question one, with a mean score of 4.75, indicates that most respondents strongly agree that it is wrong to falsify information in a financial report. Question two, with a mean score of 4.08, shows that most respondents believe their conscience will not allow them to manipulate or cook figures in a financial report. For question three, a mean score of 3.71 demonstrates that most respondents follow their conscience in determining what is right or wrong. Question four, with a mean score of 3.53, reflects that respondents moderately agree that they feel remorseful when they commit an act that conflicts with their moral values. Question five, with a mean score of 4.58 and a standard deviation of 0.907, clearly shows that respondents feel remorseful whenever their actions conflict with their ethical principles. Question six, with a mean score of 5.07, indicates that respondents strongly agree that they uphold moral values in their work as accountants. Question seven, with a mean score of 4.72, highlights that respondents link their moral values to their belief in God. Question eight, with a mean

score of 3.35, shows that respondents moderately agree that when they are about to make a mistake, they hear their conscience speak to them in the form of an “inner voice” or the “voice within.” Question nine, with a mean score of 3.39, suggests that respondents accept and correct any omissions or errors in the accounting reports they prepare. Finally, question ten, with a mean score of 3.66 and a standard deviation of 0.868, confirms that respondents recognize and act according to their conscience.

Table9:DescriptiveStatisticsonTransparency

S/N	Transparency	SA	A	M	D	SD	Agg	\bar{x}
		5	4	3	2	1		
	A transparent accounting report makes available a firm's specific information to the general public	117	46	18	4	8	839	4.35
	Transparent accounting report ensures that the disclosure of information is trustworthy, reliable, accurate, and appropriate to the time requirements and brings importance to all parties that share interest in the organization	101	59	16	8	9	814	4.22
	For an organization to be transparent, it owes the responsibility to be fair in disclosing its financial statement to those who are in need of information contained in it and the general public	42	98	47	5	1	754	3.91
	The principles/accounting standards underlying the preparation of accounting report are based on transparency	161	32	0	0	0	933	4.83
	A transparent financial reporting process carried out with excellence to instill trust and confidence in beneficiaries who wish to guarantee the fairness and accuracy of the financial information	49	14	95	17	18	638	3.31
	A transparent accounting report does not mislead its users	185	8	0	0	0	957	4.96
	The principles/financial regulations guiding an organization are based on transparency	39	74	42	21	17	676	3.50
	Accounting report that is transparent attracts investors	140	18	27	4	4	865	4.48
	A transparent accounting report depends on the credibility of the report	61	79	29	11	13	743	3.85
	A transparent accounting report makes investors to have trust in the organization management	19	41	100	14	19	606	3.14

Source:Source:ResearchDesk2021

The data presented in Table 9 reflect the responses of respondents regarding transparency in accounting. Question one, with a mean score of 4.35, indicates that most respondents strongly agree that a transparent accounting report makes available a firm's specific information to the general public. Question two, with a mean score of 4.22, shows that respondents strongly

agree that transparent accounting reports ensure that the disclosure of information is trustworthy, reliable, accurate, and appropriate to the time requirements, bringing importance to all parties with interest in the organization.

Question three, with a mean score of 3.91, indicates that respondents agree that for an organization to be transparent, it owes the responsibility to be fair in disclosing its financial statements to those in need of the information and to the general public. Question four, with a mean score of 4.83, reflects respondents' agreement that the principles and accounting standards underlying the preparation of accounting reports are based on transparency. Question five, with a mean score of 3.31, shows that respondents moderately agree that a high-quality financial reporting process provides confidence and reassurance to beneficiaries.

Question six, with a mean score of 4.96, demonstrates strong agreement that a transparent accounting report does not mislead its users. Question seven, with a mean score of 3.50, indicates agreement that the principles and financial regulations guiding an organization are based on transparency. Question eight, with a mean score of 4.48, shows strong support that transparent accounting reports attract investors. Question nine, with a mean score of 3.85, reflects agreement that a transparent accounting report depends on the credibility of the report. Finally, question ten, with a mean score of 3.14, indicates that respondents moderately agree that a transparent accounting report inspires trust in the organization's management.

Overall, the findings suggest that respondents recognize the critical role of transparency in accounting, particularly in ensuring accuracy, credibility, fairness, and trust in financial reporting.

Test of Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis

One

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between honesty and transparency.

Table 10: Correlation between Honesty and Transparency

	Honesty	Transparency
Honesty	Pearson Correlation 1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	N	193
Transparency	Pearson Correlation .773**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	193

Note: .Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 10 shows that honesty is positively related to transparency. Since $r = 0.773$, the Pearson correlation coefficient indicates a strong association between the variables under investigation. This implies that the alternative hypothesis may be accepted, and the null hypothesis rejected. Therefore, honesty is strongly related to transparency.

Hypothesis

Two

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between conscience and transparency.

Table 11: Correlation between Conscience and Transparency

	Conscience	Transparency
Conscience	Pearson Correlation 1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	N	193
Transparency	Pearson Correlation .756**	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	193

Note: .Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 11 demonstrates that transparency and conscience are positively related. Given that $r = 0.756$, the Pearson correlation coefficient indicates a strong association between the variables under investigation. This suggests that the alternative hypothesis may be accepted, and the null hypothesis rejected. Thus, transparency and conscience are significantly related.

Discussion of Findings

The results showed that transparent financial reporting and spirituality in accounting have a significant relationship.

i. The analysis of the relationship between honesty and transparency revealed that a sincere and honest person has a strong influence on accounting transparency. Similarly, an objective employee has the capacity to present a fair financial report to management. Thus, honesty has a significant relationship with transparency.

ii. The findings on the relationship between conscience and transparency revealed that employees with a strong conscience do not easily manipulate or cook figures in a financial report, as they tend to feel remorseful when they commit an act that conflicts with their moral values. Conscience significantly influences transparency. This finding is supported by Jeffrey (2006), who notes that conscience is a cognitive process that, depending on a person's moral philosophy or value system, evokes both emotion and rational association.

Summary

In Nigeria's Delta and Edo States, this study examined the connection between spirituality in accounting and transparent financial reporting. The study's conclusions are summarized as follows:

- i. Honesty has a significant relationship with transparent financial reporting.
- ii. Conscience has a significant relationship with transparent financial reporting.

Conclusion

Based on a survey research design, this study examined the relationship between spirituality in accounting and transparent financial reporting in Nigeria's Edo and Delta States. Transparency was chosen as a proxy for transparent financial reporting, while honesty and conscience represented spirituality in accounting.

A questionnaire was administered to a sample of 78 professional accountants who are members of ICAN or ANAN and work in the finance and accounts departments of state ministries, departments, and agencies. The questionnaire had a 96% success rate in gathering primary data for the investigation.

Using the Taro Yamane formula, the sample of 78 accountants was selected from a population of 166 accountants. The statistical tools for data analysis were Pearson correlation and descriptive statistics. The findings demonstrated a strong correlation between transparency and both honesty and conscience. Overall, the study found a strong correlation between spirituality in accounting and transparent financial reporting in Delta and Edo States.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. Accountants must have access to all pertinent data that could plausibly affect how intended users interpret financial data, reports, or other documents.
- ii. During the orientation process, the values of spirituality in accounting should be clearly communicated. This will provide personnel with a clear understanding of ethical balance and professional responsibility.

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